

Deliverable D-JRP1-4.2

Work Package 4

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners: BfR, RIVM, SSI, SVA,
PIWET, external partners

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IMPART WP4 – PUBLICATION IN AN OPEN-ACCESS PEER-REVIEWED JOURNAL

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INTRODUCTION

Clostridioides (C.) difficile is the major cause of human nosocomial infections but also increasingly reported within a community-associated setting. Its occurrence in human adults is often directly associated to an antibiotic treatment. Furthermore, *C. difficile* is also the causative agent of diarrhoea in several animal species leading to economic losses. Especially antibiotics that have a broad application and are frequently used, such as cephalosporins and, more recently, fluoroquinolones, are known to carry a higher risk for *C. difficile* infections (CDI) than others. To understand evolutionary processes and the epidemiological success of certain *C. difficile* lineages in correlation with antibiotic treatment policies, the surveillance of antibiotic resistances in the human as well as in the animal sector is of utmost importance.

A cost-effective alternative method to the current gold standard agar dilution (AD) is the agar disk diffusion (DD). Until recently, it has only been standardized by the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) for certain aerobic microorganisms. The aim of this study was to optimize and validate the disk diffusion method for *C. difficile*. The results of the optimization experiments as well as the validation of the method and proposal of cut-off values for the disk diffusion shall be published in a peer-reviewed journal.

STUDY DESIGN & RESULTS

A *C. difficile* strain collection was established and finally comprised of 527 strains with human, animal, environmental and food origin from collaboration partners of different European countries (Portugal, Poland, The Netherlands, Sweden, Denmark and Germany). The strains were characterized regarding their PCR-ribotypes, toxin gene profiles and minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) for clindamycin, erythromycin, imipenem, moxifloxacin, metronidazole, rifampicin, tetracycline, and vancomycin determined by agar dilution. Where possible, results were analysed for correlations with the provided data from the partner institutes. The strain collection represented more than 79 different PCR-ribotypes.

In parallel, a draft protocol for the disk diffusion testing of *C. difficile* was developed based on a literature review and already existing EUCAST recommendations for aerobic bacteria. At this time point a few studies existed for disk diffusion testing against moxifloxacin, metronidazole and vancomycin that proved the principal suitability of this method for *C. difficile* antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST). In a broader perspective we investigated the hypothesis that disk diffusion testing is a cost effective and suitable alternative to agar dilution also for other antimicrobial classes which are of interest not only from the therapeutic point of view but also with regard to epidemiological / scientific reasons. So, eight different antimicrobials from different classes (clindamycin, erythromycin, imipenem, moxifloxacin, metronidazole, rifampicin, tetracycline, and vancomycin) were chosen and the draft protocol further optimized by testing several anaerobic conditions and different culture media with a subset of up to ten *C. difficile* strains. Minimal requirements to produce reliable and comparable data were defined in an optimized method description. This optimized method was then further validated regarding its intralaboratory repeatability and interlaboratory reproducibility in an international ring trial study. These studies provided very helpful information on critical steps in the protocol and robustness of the method.

Finally, inhibition zone diameter distributions (IZDs) were determined using the optimized disk diffusion protocol for the entire *C. difficile* strain collection. Based on these distributions, cut-off values

were proposed for the identification of wildtype (non-resistant) and non-wildtype (resistant) phenotypes. The results of the resistance determination based on IZDs (DD) were correlated with those based on MICs (AD). We found high correlations for most but not all antimicrobials tested.

DISCUSSION & OUTLOOK

The publication of WP4 results and provision of the deliverable D-JRP1-4.2 has been delayed as a consequence of prior delays of the different WP4 tasks as described in the 9M- and 12M-reports as well as the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic situation. The data collection, analysis and evaluation is finished. Writing the manuscript is in progress. The manuscript will finally be discussed with the project partners, submission is planned for summer 2021.